

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Official Launch of the Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE)

Report

DELIVERABLE 1.8
MONTH 36

D1.8 – Official Launch of the Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem

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I. Planning the launch of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem

A. Organising the launch of the PEKE

1. Context

The ultimate objective of the RI4C2 project, as stated in its work plan, is to “extend the activities of the EC2U Alliance to the R&I fields, in order to transform the EC2U Alliance into the core driver of a Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE) [...] with results and outputs from eight Work Packages (WP) that will act as ‘mini-engines’ aiming at making the associated transformation a reality and delivering all components of the PEKE”. As such, it was planned to organise a specific session of the EC2U Forum to launch the PEKE at the end of the project.

However, with the new EC2U phase which started in November 2023, the next EC2U Forum will only be organised in October 2024, after the RI4C2 project ends. For that reason, it was decided, in agreement with the Management Committee on 19th October 2023, that a closing event for the RI4C2 project would be organised at the University of Poitiers on 11th and 12th of June. This event has thus served to officially launch the EC2U PEKE.

2. Event objectives

The PEKE is the result of all the activities conducted throughout the RI4C2 project, which have not only reinforced the 7 local knowledge ecosystems (composed of Education, Research, Innovation and Service to Society), but have also connected them at the European level. The RI4C2 project has thus produced the necessary tools and strategies to launch such an EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem.

In this context, the purpose of this event, entitled “**Unveiling the University of the Future: kick-off the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem**”, was threefold:

1. To showcase the overall activities and results of the RI4C2 project
2. To take stock of the RI4C2 outputs and their legacy in the EC2U Alliance
3. To move forward with the launch of the EC2U PEKE and an outlook to future projects

The crucial common thread of this event was the outlook towards the future. Indeed, the RI4C2 project has produced all the complementary elements to the EC2U Alliance to launch the PEKE, but this will not stop with the Alliance's SwafS project. The PEKE will continue to grow in the upcoming years within EC2U. Most activities conducted in the RI4C2 project will continue to develop and nurture in the EC2U consolidation phase. In addition, the activities could also continue via other project applications.

B. Defining the event programme

1. Main programme

The main programme was designed in accordance with what was defined in the work plan, but also with regards to the development of several activities within the project.

The main goal of the event was to launch the EC2U PEKE, but because it was not only one session of the EC2U Forum, the programme was further developed to also include other sessions, all supporting the launch of the PEKE.

For instance, one representative of each local Makeathon winning teams and Virtual track winning team (see D5.7 EC2U Makeathon) were invited to participate in the event to present their innovative projects to a broader audience.

Moreover, a RI4C2 Session was included in the programme as it could not be integrated in an EC2U Forum due to a timeline gap (see D8.2 RI4C2 Sessions).

Overall, the sessions were thought as a build-up to the launch of the PEKE and were the following:

Tuesday, 11th of June, 2024

- Opening Session, including opening remarks from the University of Poitiers' Rector, Vice-Rector for research and Executive Vice-Rector for the EC2U Alliance and European Networks as well as keynote speeches by DG-RTD and REA representatives.
- Talents and Creativity in the Spotlight: results from the EC2U Makeathon (presentations by Makeathon winning teams of their innovative projects)

Wednesday, 12th of June, 2024

- RI4C2 Session – Connecting people and talents: building a sustainable network
- RI4C2 Legacy
- Launch of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (closing session)

The detailed programme is presented in Annex 1.

2. Lighthouses of Innovation dedicated programme

The Lighthouses of Innovation were invited as well to the event, with a dedicated programme specifically designed for them. Indeed, as part of WP5, the Innovation experts were invited to use the mobilities available to meet one last time in the context of the project (see D5.4).

Organising such an event for the launch of the PEKE was the opportunity to include a specific programme for the Lighthouses, allowing them to reflect on the activities of the past three years, but also on the future of the network once the RI4C2 project comes to an end.

In that context, on Tuesday 11th of June afternoon, the Lighthouses of Innovation met at the H.tag shared workspace in Poitiers, to visit the premises and meet the Neoloji tech hub team. A meeting was also organised there to discuss the activities of the network and prepare a presentation for the launch of the PEKE session of Wednesday, 12th of June.

Thus, on Wednesday, 12th of June, they participated to the main event programme.

More detailed information on their meeting is available in deliverable 5.4.

Figure 1: meeting of Lighthouses of Innovation representatives at the H.tag shared workspace in Poitiers

II. Description of the event

A. Practical information

The Launch of the PEKE event attracted a total of 106 participants, with 66 attending onsite and 40 participating online.

Onsite participants originated from our partner universities: Jena, Poitiers, Turku, Salamanca, Pavia, Coimbra, and Iasi. Among them were 12 citizens who were winners of the Makeathon. The event also featured 11 Lighthouses of Innovation and included 2 representatives from the European Commission. Additionally, local stakeholders and members of academia, mostly from the University of Poitiers, comprised the majority of the attendees.

Online participants originated from our partner universities and from other European University Alliances.

B. Description of the sessions

1. General overview

As stated in section I.B, the sessions were designed to bring together all the aspects of the EC2U PEKE, culminating in its launch during the closing session.

The sessions served to take stock of the activities conducted throughout the project which contributed to forming the PEKE. The goal was also, with the closing session, to look beyond the RI4C2 project and to the continued development of the PEKE in the coming years. In sum, the event was a bridge between the present and the future, showcasing the importance of R&I activities for the EC2U Alliance.

In this section, each session is described in more details, providing an overview of the speakers, its specific goal and the topic discussed.

2. Opening session (incl. keynote speeches)

The opening session was divided into two parts. The first part was dedicated to opening remarks and included the following speakers:

- Virginie Laval, *Rector of the University of Poitiers*
- Yves Gervais, *Vice-Rector for Research at the University of Poitiers*
- Ludovic Thilly, *EC2U & RI4C2 Global Coordinator and Executive Vice-Rector for the EC2U Alliance and European Networks*

This first part was followed by keynote speeches on “The EU at the forefront of transnational knowledge ecosystems”, and included the following speakers:

- Manuel Aleixo, *Head of Unit “ERA, Spreading Excellence and Research Careers”, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission*

- Jorge Molina-Martinez, Project Adviser, Unit C.4 – Reforming European R&I and Research Infrastructures, European Research Executive Agency (REA), European Commission

In the opening remarks, Virginie Laval noted the importance of the EC2U Alliance and its partner universities as key actors of the Knowledge Square in relation to their cities, playing a crucial role in the development of their local ecosystems. In that context, the PEKE developed within the RI4C2 project has played a crucial part in supporting the Alliance's ecosystem(s).

Figure 2: Opening remarks by Virginie Laval, Rector of the University of Poitiers

In relation to Virginie Laval's remarks, Yves Gervais underlined the activities developed throughout the project, and specifically the joint R&I agenda, in which he has been directly involved. He has highlighted the success of creating such an EC2U R&I agenda, along with four new Virtual Institutes. These results will last within the EC2U Alliance as a whole.

Ludovic Thilly then took the stage to share some opening remarks as well, discussing the concept of the 4th Generation University which, as will be shown throughout the event and with the launch of the Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem, relevantly relates to the actions undertaken within the EC2U Alliance.

Following the opening remarks, Manuel Aleixo and Jorge Molina-Martinez, as keynote speakers, focused on recent policy developments and key strategies at the European Commission level.

Manuel Aleixo presented the recent developments of the ERA policy agenda, detailing the processes developed and the upcoming activities. He described some ERA actions and their outputs, notably Action 4 on research careers as well as the recently created ERA policy platform. Regarding the future developments, Manuel Aleixo notably mentioned the upcoming ERA conference on 18-19 September 2024 and the proposals for the future ERA Policy Agenda (in 2025).

Jorge Molina-Martinez has on the other hand discussed the importance of feedback to policy and how European University Alliances thus contribute to the ERA Policy Agenda. This has been done notably via the publication of three reports in 2024: one on researchers' skills, one on research assessment and one on good practices from European University Alliances projects (pilot II), which feed the new ERA policy platform. All the policy instruments related to the ERA policy agenda are available on this platform. Jorge Molina-Martinez focused in particular on the report on good practices from European University Alliances projects (pilot II), which were selected by experts.

Figure 3: presentation by Jorge Molina-Martinez, REA

These keynote speeches served to put forward the framework in which the RI4C2 project has developed, underlining the key role played by Alliances and their SwafS projects in the ERA policy agenda.

3. Makeathon session

The Makeathon Session, entitled “Talents and creativity in the spotlight: results from the EC2U Makeathon”, displayed the winning projects of the local and virtual Makeathon teams.

These innovative projects, which were developed during the 24-hour Makeathon event (on 6th and 7th of May, 2024), were presented in turn to the EC2U community, as this specific session served as a broader platform for the winning teams to promote their projects.

From the onset, it was advertised that the winning teams would receive a ticket for one of their representatives to come to Poitiers and present their project. Some partner universities took upon themselves to send a second team-member to Poitiers. Some teammates also jointly presented online and onsite.

The purpose of this session was to both give visibility to the winning projects but also to the Makeathon concept in general, an innovative format which provided 24 hours for teams to find solutions to proposed societal challenges (see D5.7 EC2U Makeathon).

The session was first introduced by Dana Strauss, from the University of Jena and WP5 Leader, as the event global coordinator. She presented the event, its purpose and roll-out.

Each winning project was then presented by the following speakers:

- **Promoting sustainable and healthy eating habits and physical activity** by João Pedro Archer Pratas (Coimbra)
- **Teleportation-Engage!** By Laurentiu-Gabriel Movilă & Mocanu Rares Georgian (Iasi)
- **The education bike against social divisions** by Maximilian Mylius & Jette Busse (Jena)
- **International student housing** by Seyedkourosh Sajjadi (Pavia)
- **Rain water and urban cool islands** by Sulayman Bouhassoun & Edoh Komi Antoine Gbetey (Poitiers)
- **Green space take-over** by Juan Pablo Meléndez Melo & Sanna Halmekangas (Turku)
- **Science communication** by Diana Kho (Linz, online European team)

Figure 4: Presentation by João Pedro Archer Pratas (Coimbra) of his team's project

Figure 5: the Makeathon award

4. RI4C2 Session

The aim of the RI4C2 session is to promote the activities of the project, its network, and to bridge activities between the RI4C2 project and the EC2U E+ project.

In the context of this event, which final aim is to launch the PEKE, the focus of the session was on the development of a large pool of stakeholders and talents, constituting an important aspect of the PEKE. As such, the session was entitled “Connecting people and talents: building a sustainable network”. A first part of the session was hence focused on “connecting people” and a second part on “empowering talents”.

The session was moderated by Tilman Turpin from the University of Poitiers and included the interventions of the following speakers:

“Connecting people”

- Dana Strauss, *Head of regional network JenaVersum, University of Jena*
- Iolanda Voda, *Lecturer PhD Habil. Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Iasi*

“Empowering talents”

- Soile Haverinen, *Head of Development, Research Services, University of Turku*
- Rita Martins dos Santos, *Project Manager, University of Coimbra*

Dana Strauss first focused her presentation on “Innovation through Collaboration”, putting forward the work conducted in WP5 to build a sustainable network with innovation experts, through different stages; from networking to collaborations. She notably took the examples of

the Recipes of Innovation publication and the organisation of the EC2U Makeathon. She thus highlighted the successful network of diverse stakeholders built throughout the project.

Iolanda Voda then presented, in a speech called “Community Engagement and the First Citizen Science Projects”, the three pilot Living Labs launched within RI4C2 and the Citizen Science projects submitted in that context. This second example underlined the important focus on Citizen Science developed within the project and its relevance in building long-lasting collaborations via the submission of common Citizen Science projects.

Figure 6: RI4C2 Session

Focusing on the topic of “Empowering talents”, Soile Haverinen discussed the “Mainstreaming Open Science”, by presenting different levels of policies (international, national and local) and their objectives. She then highlighted that those policies served to nurture the Open Science activities and resources developed within the RI4C2 project, which will feed the EC2U Alliance. The collaborations in Open Science will indeed continue beyond the RI4C2 project, with the creation of an EC2U Open Science community.

Finally, Rita Martins dos Santos presented another aspect of “Empowering talents”, with a presentation focused on “Empowering careers through the EC2U Alliance”, showing the actions taken within EC2U, and specifically within the RI4C2 project, to develop activities and tools which support careers. Notably, via actions for Gender Equality and support in researchers’ careers mobilities, but also, at the institutional level, via a specific work on the HRS4R label. The resources thus developed within the RI4C2 project will be further enriched in the EC2U Alliance.

Overall, this RI4C2 session has shown how the 3-year project has reinforced the EC2U Alliance network, by bringing different types of stakeholders onboard but also by providing tools that can support researchers and the wider EC2U Community in developing new skills.

5. RI4C2 Legacy

The RI4C2 Legacy session aimed at presenting the concrete outputs of all Work Packages (WP) and their legacy in the EC2U Alliance.

All WP leaders or their representatives were invited to present the results of their WP, the speakers were thus the following:

- WP1/WP8: Ludovic Thilly & Pauline Bordiec, *University of Poitiers*
- WP2: Ricardo Costa, *University of Salamanca*
- WP3: Jorge Noro, *University of Coimbra*
- WP4: Daniela Ovadia, *University of Pavia*
- WP5: Dana Strauss, *University of Jena*
- WP6: Ionel Mangalagiu, *University of Iași*
- WP7: Laura Niemi, *University of Turku*

The session started with an introductory video which summarised RI4C2 main outputs and their inclusion in the new EC2U consolidation phase with key figures.

Figure 7: screenshot from the RI4C2 introductory video presenting the key figures of the project

This introductory video was then followed by a detailed presentation of each WP outputs and legacy in the EC2U new phase. Hence, this session has highlighted the intricacy of the two projects, and the important role that the RI4C2 activities will play in the continuation of the EC2U Alliance. Indeed, many activities of the EC2U new phase will be based on the tools produced within RI4C2. Moreover, many resources created during the project will remain available and relevant for the EC2U community.

6. Launch of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (closing session)

Building up on all the previous sessions, the closing session was dedicated to the official launch of the EC2U PEKE.

As the PEKE is the sum of many different activities and the involvement of various stakeholders, the floor was first given to different actors involved in the project which provided their perspective on the PEKE and what it meant for future activities. Ludovic Thilly, as EC2U & RI4C2 Coordinator general, then concluded the session by describing and officially launching the PEKE.

The speakers were the following:

- João Ramalho Santos, *Vice-Rector for Research, University of Coimbra*
- Daniela Ovadia, *Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab, University of Pavia*
- Soile Haverinen, *Head of Development, Research Services, University of Turku*
- Matthias Piontek, *start-up consultant, Lighthouse of Innovation representative, Jena*
- Ricardo Costa, *Innovation Lab, Lighthouse of Innovation representative, Salamanca*
- Ludovic Thilly, *EC2U & RI4C2 Global Coordinator, University of Poitiers*

João Ramalho Santos, as Vice-Rector for Research, presented the work conducted in regards to the joint EC2U R&I agenda and the creation of four new Virtual Institutes to emphasise the role and importance of the PEKE. The Virtual Institutes will indeed remain a key element of the PEKE in the continued development of the EC2U Alliance and play a crucial role in involving researchers and students, as well as the broader EC2U academic community within the PEKE.

Daniela Ovadia, involved both in RI4C2 and EC2U E+, discussed the PEKE from the digital environment perspective. She highlighted the importance of the Connect Centre and its Knowledge Hub in favouring collaborations within the EC2U PEKE. This integration model is key to further develop the EC2U Alliance and strengthen its PEKE in the years to come.

Figure 8: Presentation by Daniela Ovidia for the launch of the PEKE

Another important aspect of the PEKE is the possibility to develop a network of shared R&I infrastructures (see D1.5 Shared R&I platforms). In that context, Soile Haverinen presented in detail Openris, a digital tool to discover, share and manage resources and services. This tool, used at the University of Turku, was identified as a good practice to facilitate the creation of an EC2U network for shared R&I infrastructures. Soile Haverinen has therefore presented the benefits of using such a platform, showcasing its relevance for future common developments in that area within EC2U.

Finally, one last perspective on the PEKE was given by two Lighthouses of Innovation representatives, following their meeting the day before; Matthias Piontek and Ricardo Costa. Reflecting on the activities of the Lighthouses of Innovation in the past three years, they have put forward that stakeholders are also key actors of the EC2U PEKE. With the results produced within RI4C2 and the future activities planned for the network, they will remain involved in the activities of the Alliance and play a crucial role within the PEKE.

Figure 9: Presentation by Matthias Piontek and Ricardo Costa for the launch of the PEKE

As the session, and the event, were coming to an end, Ludovic Thilly concluded the session by presenting what the PEKE is concretely, detailing the different actors (academia, cities, citizens, innovators, private companies, etc...) which take part in local knowledge ecosystems. Thanks to the activities of the RI4C2 project, those local knowledge ecosystems have been connected at the European level, creating the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem. This was also the opportunity to present the benefits of such a PEKE for people and for institutions. Finally, and together with the audience, the PEKE was officially launched.

Figure 10: Ludovic Thilly officially launches the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem

C. Communication on the event

1. Pre-event communication

To devise the communication strategy for the Launch of the PEKE, the EC2U global communication team collaborated with the RI4C2 team, initiating the planning process with a meeting in January. Given that the project included the Makeathon event in May, which required public participation, it was decided to prioritise communications for the Makeathon until its conclusion. Consequently, the official communication for the Launch of PEKE started in May, ensuring to have the full attention of our primary audience, comprising mainly EC2U/RI4C2 members and partners.

The communication strategy axed mainly social media platforms such as LinkedIn, X, Instagram for the pre-event contents, listed below:

- LinkedIn:

EC2U Alliance
1401 abonnés
1 mois

📌 Join us for the **#RI4C2** Event: "Unveiling the University of the Future: Kick-off the **#EC2U** Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem" 🌐 🗓️

📅 Dates: June 11th and 12th
📍 Location: **Université de Poitiers** and online

This event, gathering esteemed speakers from the European Commission, the RI4C2 project team, and various stakeholders will be the opportunity to bridge the present and future of **#Research** and **#Innovation** in the EC2U Alliance.

🌟 Highlights:

- Insightful presentations on the RI4C2 project outputs and future projects
- The EC2U **#Makeathon** showcasing innovative projects from winning teams
- Networking opportunities

🔗 Info & registration: <https://lnkd.in/eH7DKzs>

Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku | Universidade de Coimbra | Universidad de Salamanca | Università di Pavia | Johannes Kepler Universität Linz | Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași

EC2U Alliance
1401 abonnés
3 sem.

🔥 We are less than one week away from the **#RI4C2** Event "Kick-off the **#EC2U** Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem: Unveiling the University of the Future"

📅 11-12 June
📍 Univ. of Poitiers & online

This event will be the opportunity to take stock of the activities conducted during the 3 years of the RI4C2 project, but also to put forward their continuation within the EC2U Alliance.

Don't miss out on shaping the future of universities: <https://lnkd.in/eH7DKzs>

#innovation #research #UniversityOfTheFuture #Makeathon

Friedrich Schiller University Jena | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku | Universidade de Coimbra | Universidad de Salamanca | Università di Pavia | Johannes Kepler Universität Linz | Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași

UNIVERSITY OF THE FUTURE - EUROPEAN KNOWLEDGE ECOSYSTEM

Session 16:00 - 18:15 | Talents and talents: spotlight: results from the network

Session 14:00 - 15:30 | RI4C2 network

Session 16:00 - 17:00 | Launch European Knowledge Ecosystem

Speakers include: João Pedro Archer, Laurentiu-Gabriel Movilă & Maximilian Mylius, Seyedkourosh, Sulayman Bouhassoun & Edoh, Juan Pablo Meléndez Melo & Diana Kho, Pauline Bordiec & Ludovic Thilly, Ricardo Costa, Jorge Noro, Daniela Ovadia, Dana Strauß, Ionel Mangalagiu, Laura Niemelä, João Ramalho Santos, Daniela Ovadia, Salla Haverinen, Lighthouses of Innovation, Ludovic Thilly.

Figure 11: LinkedIn post on the EC2U account

- Instagram:

ec2u_alliance 🇪🇺 Join us for the #RI4C2 Event: "Unveiling the University of the Future: Kick-off the #EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem" 🌍🎓

📅 Dates: June 11th and 12th
📍 Location: @univpoitiers & online

This event, gathering esteemed speakers from the European Commission, the RI4C2 project team, and various stakeholders will be the opportunity to bridge the present and future of #Research and #Innovation in the EC2U Alliance.

- 🌟 Highlights:
- Insightful presentations on the RI4C2 project outputs and future projects
 - The EC2U #makeathon showcasing innovative projects from winning teams
 - Networking opportunities

🔗 Info & registration: (link in bio)
28 mai • Voir la traduction

Figure 12: pre-event Instagram post

- X:

Figure 13: first tweet post on May 28

Figure 14: one week left reminder post on June 5

2. Communication during the event

During the event, the EC2U global coordination team created threads on the platform X and stories on Instagram to keep followers updated on the event's progress.

Instagram:

To keep our followers updated during the event, several Instagram stories were published, providing real-time updates and engaging our audience throughout the proceedings.

X:

Figure 15: D-Day post from the University of Poitiers's official X account

Figure 16: X thread on the first day of the event (11/06)

Figure 17: X thread on the second day (12/06)

Figure 18: X post on the second day of the event with an RI4C2 achievements video

3. Post-event communication

Post-event communication is crucial for showcasing the achievements of the event and expressing gratitude to the participants who attended both onsite and online. To accomplish this, the platform X was utilised to share content and posted videos of the event's replays on the EC2U YouTube Channel. Internally, a thank you email was sent to all participants.

X:

Figure 19: post event X post on June 21

YouTube:

The sessions are available on the [EC2U YouTube Channel](#).

Figure 20: creation of a new playlist dedicated to the event

D. Feedback from participants

A feedback survey was sent to all participants at the end of these 2 days to measure their satisfaction rate. 42 participants answered the survey: 23 answered to all questions and 19 partially responded to the survey. Here are a few graphics with selected questions and the results obtained:

Figure 22: survey question about the expectations of the participants

Figure 23: survey question about the overall experience of the participants

Figure 24: Survey question about the quality of the content and presentations during the event

- **What was the most valuable part of the event for you?**

Figure 25: word cloud summarising feedback responses from participants

As shown in the graphs, participants were satisfied with the event and its programme.

The word cloud underlines that, whether attending in person or virtually, participants greatly valued the collegial atmosphere of the event, the visibility it provided into the European Universities Network, and the multitude of new collaboration ideas that emerged during these two days.

Here is one quote from the survey summarising this positive feedback and the main achievements of the event:

“My biggest takeaway from the event was the effort of the project team to improve innovation in research together with citizens.” – A participant

III. Concluding remarks

The launch of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem was successfully achieved thanks to an event which shed light on all the actors involved in the project and on the activities which were conducted throughout the RI4C2 project and have led to the launch of the PEKE.

However, such a PEKE is not set in stone and is necessarily a continuous work in progress, as it must be nurtured with additional activities and the involvement of all stakeholders who are part of the EC2U community. Therefore, the PEKE will not end with the RI4C2 project, but on the contrary, as it has been underlined during the event, will continue to develop within the EC2U consolidation phase.

Hence, the PEKE will continuously be fed with new joint activities and collaborations on all aspects of the Knowledge Square, and will remain the core driver of the EC2U Alliance. On top of the activities to continue in the new EC2U Erasmus+ funding period, other projects could be developed via additional funding instruments so as to ensure that all aspects of the PEKE can continue to grow.

Finally, the RI4C2 project has reached its ultimate goal with the launch of the PEKE, which showcases the fulfilment of all the planned activities and the production of concrete results. This three-year project thus came to an end with this event, but as indicated in its name, the “launch” of the PEKE shows that this EC2U sister project only started to transform the R&I dimension of the Alliance. This foundation is in the end the catalyst for future developments of joint R&I collaborations within EC2U.

IV. Annexes

A. Annex 1: event programme

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

Unveiling the University of the Future: Kick-off the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem

University of Poitiers
B.U. Lettres – La Ruche, Poitiers, France
Online: [Webex](#)
11th & 12th June 2024

Tuesday 11th June
14:00 – 18:00 CET

14:00 – 15:30	Opening Session
14:00 – 14:30	Opening remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Virginie Laval, Rector of the University of Poitiers - Yves Gervais, Vice-Rector for Research - Ludovic Thilly, EC2U & RI4C2 Global Coordinator and Executive Vice-Rector for EC2U Alliance and European Networks
14:30 – 15:30	Keynote speeches on “The EU at the forefront of transnational knowledge ecosystems” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manuel Aleixo, Head of Unit “ERA, Spreading Excellence and Research Careers”, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission - Jorge Molina-Martinez, Project Adviser, Unit C.4 – Reforming European R&I and Research Infrastructures, European Research Executive Agency (REA), European Commission
15:30 – 16:00	Coffee Break
16:00 – 18:00	Talents and creativity in the spotlight: results from the EC2U Makeathon
16:00 – 16:10	Introduction and context Dana Strauß, University of Jena
16:10 – 16:20	Promoting sustainable and healthy eating habits and physical activity João Pedro Archer Pratas (Coimbra)

16:20 – 16:30	Teleportation-Engage! Laurențiu-Gabriel Movilă & Mocanu Rares Georgian (Iasi)
16:30 – 16:40	The education bike against social divisions Maximilian Mylius & Jette Busse (Jena)
16:40 – 16:50	International student housing Seyedkourosh Sajjadi (Pavia)
16:50 – 17:15	Break
17:15 – 17:25	Rain water and urban cool islands Sulayman Bouhassoun & Edoh Komi Antoine Gbetey (Poitiers)
17:25 – 17:35	Green space take-over Juan Pablo Meléndez Melo & Sanna Halmekangas (Turku)
17:35 – 17:45	Science communication Diana Kho (online European team)
17:45 – 18:00	Q&As

**Wednesday 12th June
9:00 – 18:30 CET**

9:00 – 12:15	RI4C2 Session – Connecting people and talents: building a sustainable network
9:00 – 9:15	Introductory remarks - Tilman Turpin, <i>University of Poitiers</i>
9:15 – 10:15	Connecting people - “Innovation through Collaboration”, Dana Strauß, <i>Head of regional network JenaVersum, University of Jena</i> - “Community Engagement and the First Citizen Science Initiatives”, Iolanda Voda, <i>Lecturer Ph.D. Habil., Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Iasi</i>
10:15 – 10:45	Coffee Break
10:45 – 11:45	Empowering talents - “Mainstreaming Open Science”, Soile Haverinen, <i>Head of Development, Research Services, University of Turku</i> - “Empowering Careers through the EC2U Alliance”, Rita Martins dos Santos, <i>Project Manager, University of Coimbra</i>
11:45 – 12:00	Concluding remarks - Tilman Turpin, <i>University of Poitiers</i>

12:00 – 12:15 **Group picture**

12:15 – 14:00 **Lunch break (1st Floor, La Ruche)**

14:00 – 15:30 **RI4C2 Legacy**

Introductory video on RI4C2 results followed by a general presentation of main RI4C2 results and outputs and their inclusion in the new EC2U consolidation phase

Presented by the RI4C2 WP Leaders:

- WP1/WP8: Pauline Bordiec & Ludovic Thilly, *University of Poitiers*
- WP2: Ricardo Costa, *University of Salamanca*
- WP3: Jorge Noro, *University of Coimbra*
- WP4: Daniela Ovadia, *University of Pavia*
- WP5: Dana Strauß, *University of Jena*
- WP6: Ionel Mangalagiu, *University of Iasi*
- WP7: Laura Niemi, *University of Turku*

15:30 – 16:00 **Coffee Break**

16:00 – 17:00 **Launch of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem**

Series of speeches providing examples on how concrete RI4C2 results will continue to give life to the PEKE in the future (joint R&I agenda and infrastructures / EC2U Connect Centre / network of Lighthouses), especially for future joint research projects or other collaborative projects.

- João Ramalho Santos, *Vice-Rector for Research, University of Coimbra* & Jorge Noro, *Coordinator of the Institute of Interdisciplinary Research, University of Coimbra*
- Daniela Ovadia, *Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab, University of Pavia*
- "Open and visible research infrastructures", Soile Haverinen, *Head of Development, University of Turku*
- Lighthouses of Innovation Representatives
- Ludovic Thilly, *EC2U & RI4C2 Global Coordinator and Executive Vice-Rector for EC2U Alliance and European Networks, University of Poitiers*

17:00 – 18:30 **Closing cocktail**

B. Annex 2: List of registered onsite participants

Title	Institution
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Institutional representative	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Student	University of Poitiers
Institutional representative	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Academic staff/researcher	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Academic staff/researcher	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Institutional representative	University of Poitiers
Administrative staff	University of Poitiers
Non-academic stakeholder	Poitiers
Student	University of Coimbra
Student	University of Iasi
Student	University of Turku
Student	University of Linz
Municipality representative	Poitiers
Academic staff/researcher	University of Jena
Non-academic stakeholder	University of Jena
Student	University of Jena
Administrative staff	University of Jena
Administrative staff	University of Jena
Citizen	University of Jena

Academic staff/researcher	University of Jena
Student	University of Jena
Student	University of Pavia
Student	University of Turku
Student	University of Poitiers
Academic staff/researcher	University of Salamanca
Administrative staff	University of Salamanca
Student	University of Iasi
Academic staff/researcher	University of Coimbra
Institutional representative	University of Coimbra
Administrative staff	University of Coimbra
Academic staff/researcher	University of Pavia
Administrative staff	University of Pavia
Academic staff/researcher	University of Iasi
Non-academic stakeholder	Coimbra
Non-academic stakeholder	Poitiers
Non-academic stakeholder	Turku
Administrative staff	University of Turku

C. Annex 3: Photos of the event

Participants group picture – day 2 (12/06)

Makeathon winning teams representatives – day 2 (12/06)

This report reflects only the author's view and does not reflect the opinions of the European Union or the European Commission. The Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.